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SWOC Analysis of the Policies, Plans, Programs and Plant Facilities for Tourism Promotion in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

India has a very rich cultural and mythological heritage that enriches its traditions. Most of the mythological literature states that Uttar Pradesh of India is the land of incarnations. Mainly the two incarnations of Lord Vishnu named Lord Ram and Lord Krishna were born in Ayodhya and Mathura. The exile route of Lord Ram is known as Ramayana Circuit and is being developed by the government under the Swadesh Darshan Scheme an initiative of the Ministry of Tourism. There is vast potential for spiritual/religious tourism and the hospitality industry in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh. But each destination has some strengths and weaknesses that can boost its dimensions or demolish it. Similarly, it may cause various opportunities and challenges during its resurrection period. Therefore, an attempt is made in this study to analyse the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges of the policies, plans, programs, and plant facilities for tourism promotion in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh. The findings of the study will help stakeholders and government to enhance their understanding about the impact of the policies, plans, programs, and plant facilities and allow them the advancement of same through SWOC analysis.

Keywords: SWOC Analysis, Ramayana Circuit, 4P's Tourism Promotion

Introduction

SWOC Analysis is an important method to analyse tourism development. Some scholars use the indicators of travel and tourism opportunities and challenges, while some scholars use the strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat (SWOT) as a technique for identifying

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the strategy and development of tourism (Bhatia, 2013). Both the abbreviations are similar in meaning to SWOC and SWOT. Relatively the result of SWOC analysis reinforces the difficult situations of policies, plans, programs, and plant facilities for their improvement by government and other stakeholders. It is a structured planning method used to evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges involved in a project or venture to promote tourism activities by identifying the internal and external factors that are favourable or unfavourable to achieve the objectives of the tourism and hospitality industry. SWOC analysis is a term to explain the internal strengths and weaknesses of a project and the development opportunities and challenges facing that project in a wide context of policies, plans, programs, and plant facilities. SWOC analysis is a systematic documentation of these aspects and the strategy that imitates the best match among them. The reason behind this method is that an effective strategy maximizes project strength and opportunities on the other hand it minimizes its weaknesses and challenges. 4P's for tourism promotion are discussed as follows:

POLICY: The broad framework of ideas and values within which decisions are taken and action or inaction is pursued by governments for solving complex and conflicting problems (Brooks, 1989). According to (Bholey, 2014) Governments are expected to deliver a large number of social good for growth, stability and development of society and to ensure that they make an equally large number of public policies.

PLAN: It is a specific application of the decision that seeks to influence the future and it is to define objectives or results to be achieved (Victoria, 2019). A plan is a bridge that produces goals and ways to accomplish activities and resources of objectives.

PROGRAM: A program is a set of several projects to achieve its target while a project is created to deliver a specified output as efficiently as possible (Weaver, 2010). Programs focus on the coordination of several related projects and other activities to deliver outcomes that benefit the organization.

PLANT FACILITY: It refers to all the structures, types of machinery, pieces of equipment, services, buildings, activities, investments, and piping systems for the promotion and development of a particular purpose.

Literature Review

Spiritual and religious tourism enhances religious motivation, though the pilgrims and tourists also visit religious destinations for other purposes like well-being, knowledge, awareness, and attaining spiritual ambiance (Vukonic, 1996). Religion, spirituality, and pilgrimage are appreciated as significant phenomena in tourism, and refers religious tourism as diverged into the formal and the popular. The formal pilgrimage is motivated to fulfill religious commitments, while the popular pilgrimage identifies and is oriented towards non-religious but personal development and well-being (Cohen, 1979). Ramayana Circuit is one of the fifteen thematic circuits recently announced by the MoT, Government of India under “Swadesh Darshan Scheme” (PIB, 2019). The Ministry has initially identified fifteen destinations under the Ramayana Circuit theme namely Ayodhya, Nandigram, Shringverpur and Chitrakoot (Uttar Pradesh), Sitamarhi, Buxar and Darbhanga (Bihar), Chitrakoot (Madhya Pradesh), Mahendragiri (Odisha), Jagdalpur (Chattisgarh), Nashik and Nagpur (Maharashtra), Bhadrachalam (Telangana), Hampi (Karnataka) and Rameshwaram (Tamil Nadu) for the expansion and development of the cultural, spiritual, religious, and heritage values of Ramayana. Spiritual tourism has been recognized as an important part of the tourism industry associated with India. Statistics shows that several oral, archaeological, mythological literature, and peoples’ engrossment with spiritual experiences and their explorations to various areas of India to engage in various spiritual activities (Rinschede, 1992). (James, 2000) states that spiritual tourism holds a large part of tourism industry and still growing in India, irrespective of the uncertainty related to the economic, social, and political issues. Spiritual tourism is budding in all geographic regions, especially in India, because of its acceptance by global tourists. Several Indian ashrams and temples that accommodate a large number of local and foreign spiritual tourists traveling for spiritual and religious motives are significant examples of progress (Sharpley & Sundaram, 2005). The government is preparing to employ the services of tourism experts and other stakeholders like state government, agencies, tour operators, and different organizations to accomplish this task and is ready to deploy the infrastructural project, plans, and programs for the development of this circuit (TOI, 2021). It will promote packaged tours to visit religious places and would be beneficial for the development of the hospitality industry for accommodating and other plant facilities required by the tourists.

Objective of the Study

- ❖ To analyse the internal strengths and weaknesses of 4P's for tourism promotion in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh.
- ❖ To explore the external opportunities and challenges of 4P's for tourism promotion in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh.
- ❖ To suggest measures to the Government for improvement of Policies, Plans, Programs and Plant Facilities based on SWOC analysis.

Research Methodology

Modus operandi of this research is based on primary and secondary sources of data that are used in this research work. Primary data as collected through the questionnaire, discussion and interaction with domestic and foreign tourists visiting the study area. Besides this, secondary data is collected from the official website of Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI) issued by World Economic Forum in 2021, UNWTO, MoT, Government of Uttar Pradesh and other different journals, magazines, newspapers, and books.

SWOC Analysis

- i. **Strengths:** India have a vast canvas for tourism and hospitality industry including its bio-diversity, geo-diversity, climate, landscape, natural resources, culture, traditions, and heritage. Spirituality, religious expectations, wellness, adventure activities, cuisines, and unique cultural activities can be experienced here in different parts of the country. *“India is a cradle of the human race, the birthplace of human speech, the mother of history, the grandmother of legend, and the great-grandmother of tradition,”* said by Mark Twain. Mark Twain was an American author who lectured across the Indian subcontinent for over two months and narrated his experiences of India, Australia, and South Africa in his travelogue *“Following the Equator (1897)”* (Sharma, 2017). Pro-tourism approach of Indian government is continuously strengthening the industry. The National Tourism Policy 2022 has set a new vision on a high trajectory of growth and prosperity. NTP 2022 is a holistic framework for sustainable and responsible growth of the tourism and hospitality sector in the country. The Policy would improve framework conditions for tourism development, supporting tourism industries, strengthening tourism support pillars, and

developing tourism sub-sectors. The policy is architected around six key guiding principles, plans, programs, five national tourism missions, and eight strategic pillars supported by a decorative institutional and Governance Framework. Indian tourism industry has geared up with 54th rank in the world as per the latest Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report (TTCR, 2022) issued by World Economic Forum in 2022 and secured 14th rank in World Tourism Receipts.

International Tourist Arrival (in million)	7.0
International Tourism Receipts (in USD billion)	8.7
International Tourism Expenditure (in USD billion)	14.3
Tourism as share of total Exports (in %)	1.4
Tourism as share of GDP (in %)	2.6
Total Employment (in 1000)	29,683

Source: UNWTO Tourism Data Dashboard. **Table 01:** Indian Tourism Statistics at a Glance 2022

Target of National Tourism Policy 2022	2023	2030	2040	2047
International Tourist Arrival (in million)	13	25	56	100
Domestic Tourist Visits (in billion)	02	04	10	15
Foreign Exchange Earnings (in USD billion)	30	56	175	400
Employment (in million)	88	137	257	400
Tourism GDP (in USD billion)	143	248	550	1000

Source: National Tourism Policy 2022, MoT, Government of India. **Table 02:** Target of NTP 2022

India has more than 1600 local languages but due to the impact of the colonial era in most of the region English language is commonly spoken and understood all over India which gives India an added advantage in comparison to other Asia-Pacific Nations. India is a union of 28 states and 08 union territories in which Uttar Pradesh is the largest state in terms of size and population. Uttar Pradesh has a rich potential for religious, spiritual, cultural, and historical tourism along with Ramayana Circuit, Mahabharat Circuit, Braj Circuit, and Buddhist Circuit.

Handicrafts, Jewellery, Awadhi Cuisine, Chicken Embroidery, and other merchandise are very popular among tourists.

- ii. **Weaknesses:** India is the biggest democracy of the world which survives on its typical bureaucracy. Mostly it has been seen that tourism is not confined to tourism service providers or one particular experience, but the overall experience of atmospheric construct and destination. It is the destinations, which have to contend and succeed. Statistics of tourism-centric investment reflect that a large amount of plant facilities were developed at the time of international events and conferences. There are some occasions like Commonwealth Games, Asian, G 20, Kumbh Mela, and Dipotsav are global events that have drawn the attention of government and bureaucracy towards the development of tourism infrastructure. Tourism is based on AAA – Attractions, Accessibility, and Accommodation closely integrated with several other industries like hotels, restaurants, aviation, railway, roadways, healthcare, and entertainment etc., the combined weaknesses of all the sectors make it more vulnerable (Agrawal, 2016). The condition of the hotel industry is very poor in this region as per data from UNWTO India has only 0.2 beds per 1,000 population. While focusing on Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh, the nearest international airport is 150 km away from Ayodhya, and the a shortage of connecting trains makes it more vulnerable. Tourism stakeholders are still approaching faith and belief of people to promote tourism in Ramayana Circuit. There is a huge gap in marketing, digitalization, innovation, and technical strategies to be a collective support system for destination development. Policy makers are self-obsessed and still focusing on mystical charm, and ancient civilization, but India has a lot more to offer better than any other Asia Pacific nation.

City	Indian Tourist	Foreign Tourist
Ayodhya	23909014	1465
Prayagraj	26045271	1895
Chitrakoot	3719223	0
Total	53673508	3360

iii. Opportunities: In 2022, the tourism sector contributed USD 23 billion to the GDP and provided employment to 29.6 million people. By the end of 2030, these numbers are expected to increase to USD 56 billion and 137 million respectively. It means that the tourism industry will account for USD 248 billion of India's GDP in 2030 (*Table 01, Table 02*). National Tourism Policy 2022 and Uttar Pradesh New Tourism Policy 2022 are dedicated to destination-centric programs and offers 10% to 25% subsidy on investment in tourism and hospitality sectors. FDI, MICE, YUVA, Agri, Niche, Spiritual/Religious, Eco, Wildlife, Cuisine, Adventure, Wellness, Budget Hotel, Farm Stay, Homestays, Naturopathy Centres, and River Cruise are the other joint ventures in UP Tourism Policy for the promotion of tourism. There are some special provisions for financial assistance, incentives, and concessions for the development of ICT and Start-Ups to promote tourism. The construction of Shri Ram Janmabhoomi Mandir in Ayodhya, Nishad Raj Guhya Park in Shringverpur, Ropeway and Glass Surface in Chitrakoot, several museums, meditation centres, and Bundelkhand Express Way is going to unlock the next level of tourist involvements. India achieved 07 million of foreign tourist arrivals - FTA in 2022 and simultaneously Uttar Pradesh hold first position in terms of Indian visitors and achieved third position in FTA.

Source: Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of U.P. **Table 03:** District-wise tourist arrivals in 2022

iv. Challenges: In last fifteen years, global peacefulness has dropped by more than 3%, in correlation with Global Peace Index 2022. Past and present conflicts, the pandemic and our political and cultural polarization are the main perpetrators (VENTURA, 2023) state that the economic impact of violence on the global economy is quantifiable USD 17.5 trillion in purchasing-power parity terms, or 12.9% of total global GDP. India holds 126th rank in Global Peace Index 2023 that is a challenge in terms of safety and security. Weakness of law and order has a negative impact on the decision-making process of tourist and create uncertainty in destination image. Safety and security are an issue specifically for solo and women travellers. People avoid the destinations which have the same kind of challenges. India is blessed with diversity in climates but sometimes it creates

challenges like floods, rains, scorching, cloud burst, and landslide which are harmful for life and business. Illegal infrastructural development for tourism can lead to environmental imbalances. Unregulated constructions, disposal of waste, destruction of forests, depletion of water levels, and pollution caused by vehicles can be threatening to the environment. Beggars, poverty, theft, discrimination, and billingsgate are the social challenges that annoy the visitors and usually, they decide to go back.

<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Strengths</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spiritual and Religious Attractions • Culture and Tradition • Diversity • Faith and Belief • Programs 	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Weaknesses</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility • Accommodation • Lack of marketing • Plans • Plant facilities
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Opportunities</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourist Arrivals • Employment • Policy • Constructions <p>(Shri Ram Janmabhoomi, Statue of Nishad Raj, Ropeways etc.)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Challenges</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety and Security • Social and Political Issues • Environmental Issues • Skill and Education

Table 04: SWOC Analysis of 4P's in Ramayana Circuit of Uttar Pradesh.

Conclusions

Tourism and hospitality industry has a major share in foreign exchange, employment, and GDP. As statistics shows that the tourism industry is continuously speeding up its growth and India also has a target for the future then it is the responsibility of policymakers to take the right step in favor of the industry and ensure the implementation of National Tourism Policy 2022 and UP Tourism Policy 2022 to achieve their objectives by 2030 and respectively. SWOC analysis of policies, plans, programs, and plant facilities must be carried out from time to time. Tourism is a subject of state government in federal India but major international policies, visas, immigration, aviation, railways, national highways, international threats, and other several issues are the

responsibilities of the Government of India. So, both must create an ecosystem for tourists to experience and visit India with ease. In sum, there are some key factors that could contribute as significant pillars of inbound tourism such as new attractions, plant facilities, rich cultural resources and geographical diversity, government initiatives, plans, and policies, multiple marketing and promotional activities, healthy economic growth levels, being the host nations for international events etc. The stakeholders of tourism and hospitality industry should make the best possible use of such potential so that Indian tourism industry can strongly stand with high potential.

References

- Agrawal, V. (2016). A Review of Indian Tourism Industry with SWOT Analysis. *J Tourism Hospit* 5, 196.
- Bhatia, A. (2013). SWOT Analysis of Indian tourism Industry. *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management*, 44-49.
- Bholey, M. (2014). Public Policy and Design: an Interdisciplinary Approach to. *Global Journal of Finance and Management.*, 151-156.
- Brooks, S. (1989). *Public Policy in Canada*. Canada: McClelland & Stewart.
- Cohen, E. (1979). A phenomenology of tourist experiences. *Sociology*, vol. 13, 179-201.
- James, N. (2000). Double identity in Orissa's Golden Triangle. *Antiquity*, Vol. 74, 682-686.
- MoT. (2023, April 04). *Ministry of Tourism, Government of India*. Retrieved from <https://tourism.gov.in/>
- PIB. (2019, July 02). <https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=191116>. Retrieved from Press Information Bureau : <https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=191116>
- Rinschede, G. (1992). Forms of religious tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol. 19, 51-67.
- Sharma, S. (2017). Mark Twain's India: The Private-Public Divide in Following the Equator. *The Mark Twain Annual*, Vol. 15(1), 22-37.
- Sharpley, R., & Sundaram, P. (2005). Tourism: A sacred journey The case of Ashram tourism, India. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, Vol. 07, 161-171.

- TOI. (2021, August 30). *Ramayana Circuit straddles 15 Indian towns*. Retrieved from Times of India: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/lucknow/ramayana-circuit-straddles-15-indian-towns/articleshow/85751613.cms>
- TTCR. (2022). *Travel & Tourism Development Index 2021*. World Economic Forum.
- UPTourism. (2023, April 08). *Uttar Pradesh Tourism*. Retrieved from uptourism: <https://uptourism.gov.in/en>
- VENTURA, L. (2023, September 15). *World's Most Peaceful Country 2023 — Global Peace Index*. Retrieved from Global Finance: <https://www.gfmag.com/global-data/non-economic-data/most-peaceful-countries>
- Victoria, A. (2019). *Professional Planning*. 10.13140/RG.2.2.18475.69925.
- Vukonic, B. (1996). *Tourism and Religion translated by Sanja Matesic*. Oxford, Pergamon Press.
- Weaver, P. (2010). UNDERSTANDING PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS OH, THERE'S A DIFFERENCE. *PMI Global Congress* (pp. 02-17). Melbourne: Mosaic Project Services Pty Ltd.